

**Consistency of Serial CSF alpha-Synuclein Seed Amplification Assay Results in the Parkinson's Progression
Marker Initiative
Code Sharing README file**

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to provide guidance to assist a third-party researcher in understanding the organization and presentation of the statistical analysis code included in the Zenodo folder [10.5281/zenodo.18894423].

The shared code was created to perform analyses for the article, "Consistency of Serial CSF alpha-Synuclein Seed Amplification Assay Results in the Parkinson's Progression Marker Initiative", currently available in preprint. This code was created to analyze data accessed from the PPMI database (RRID:SCR_006431) on January 5, 2026. As the PPMI database is always evolving, it is possible that the code may not work if the database has changed since the date the code was created.

Analytic datasets are not included in the submission. Researchers can request access to PPMI data at the PPMI Study website (<https://www.ppmi-info.org/access-data-specimens/download-data>).

2. Software

All shared codes were written using SAS 9.4.

3. Employed Datasets

The shared code references the following datasets:

- all_in_saa_listing_05jan2026 – A wide-formatted data of SAA results and clinical/demographic variables relevant to this analysis.
- neg_to_pos_subset_05jan2026 – The subset dataset of participants that converted from SAA negative to positive/type I.
- all_saa_long_05jan2026 – A long-formatted dataset of SAA results.

4. File Instructions

The following files are included with the submission:

1. Table 1 - Longitudinal Results Across Group (6/3/26)
2. Tables 2 and S2 – Longitudinal Consistency (6/3/26)
3. Table S1 – Longitudinal Results with Demographics (6/3/26)
4. Tables S3a and S3b - Longitudinal Consistency in Capped Prodromals (6/3/26)

5. Figure S1A, S1B, and S1C - Timing of CSF aSyn-SAA testing (6/3/26)
6. In Text Results (6/3/26)
7. Macro Codes (6/3/26)

4.1. Table 1 - Longitudinal Results Across Group

Generates tables displaying the number of participants with at least 1 and >1 SAA results by cohort and subgroup.

4.2. Tables 2 and S2 – Longitudinal Consistency

Generates tables of longitudinal SAA consistency among those with initial positive/type I results and negative results, including demographic information, by cohort and subgroup.

4.3. Table S1 – Longitudinal Results with Demographics

Generates tables displaying the number of participants with >1 SAA results, including demographic information, by cohort and subgroup.

4.4 Tables S3a and S3b - Longitudinal Consistency in Capped Prodromals

Generates tables of longitudinal SAA consistency among prodromal participants with initial positive/type I results and negative results, capped at 2 years.

4.5 Figure S1A, S1B, and S1C - Timing of CSF aSyn-SAA testing

Generates UpSet plots of SAA visit patterns by cohort, indicating converters from SAA negative to positive/type I results.

4.6 In Text Results

Generates raw output for in-text numbers, including:

- Information on the duration between SAA visits overall and in the subset of prodromal converters from SAA negative to positive/type I results.
- Consistency among assays, including when 150hr assays are excluded.

4.7 Macro Codes

Contains the SAS macros employed in the table and in-text results codes above.

5. Acknowledgements

Codes are shared in compliance with the open access policy for Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) (<https://parkinsonsroadmap.org/open-access-policy/>).

6. Disclaimer

Manuscript authors will not provide assistance in the use of the shared code. If a potential error is found in the shared code, please contact the lead author.